

References

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Synthesis and Biological Screening of 5-(Nitroaryl)-substituted-oxa/thiadiazoles

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In view of the fact that a large number of oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles exhibit biological activities¹, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise the title compounds and evaluate their biological activities. Thus 2-amino-5-(nitroaryl)-oxa-3,4-diazoles² (3) was obtained from the semicarbazones (1) using Br₂/AcOH, while 2-amino-5-(nitroaryl)-thia-3,4-diazoles³ (4) were obtained by oxidative cyclisation of substituted thiosemicarbazones using FeCl₃/EtOH. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their analytical and ir and ¹H nmr spectral data.

Experimental

All melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP-2000 spectrophotometer

Compd. no.	$\nu_{\max}$ (cm ⁻¹)	δ
3a	3 650 (OH), 3 500, 3 400 (NH), 1 630 (C=N), 1 540, 1 350 (NO ₂), 1 020 (C-O-C)	6.28, 7.20, 7.4 (1H, s, each Ar-H).
b	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 025	3.58 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.24, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
c	3 500, 3 408, 1 628, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	1.23 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.06 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.22, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
d	3 510, 3 410, 1 630, 1 540, 1 360, 1 020	3.59 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.8 (1H, s, each ArH)
e	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (6H, t, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.99 (4H, q, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
f	3 510, 3 400, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.08 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
g	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	1.22 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.52 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.08 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.34, 7.38 (1H, s, each ArH)
4a	3 650, 3 510, 3 400, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	6.28, 7.20, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
b	3 500, 3 400, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 010	3.58 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.24, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
c	3 510, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 360, 1 010	1.23 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 4.06 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.22, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
d	3 500, 3 410, 1 620, 1 550, 1 350, 1 020	3.59 (6H, s, 2 × OCH ₃), 6.28, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
e	3 500, 3 410, 1 630, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (6H, t, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.99 (4H, q, J 6Hz, 2 × OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.3, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
f	3 510, 3 400, 1 610, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.07 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)
g	3 510, 3 410, 1 610, 1 540, 1 350, 1 020	1.21 (3H, t, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 3.50 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.07 (2H, q, J 6Hz, OCH ₂ CH ₃), 6.32, 7.4 (1H, s, each ArH)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.